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Tissue and Serum Concentrations of Time-Dependent Antibiotics in Infected Diabetic Foot Ulcers by Bolus or Continuous Administration: The Randomised DFIATIM Trial

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ABSTRACT

Aims: The clinical effectiveness of antibiotic (ATB) therapy in patients with infected diabetic foot ulcers (iDFUs) depends on achieving sufficient ATB concentrations in both serum and peripheral tissues. This study evaluated the availability and bactericidal activity of the time-dependent ATBs—ceftazidime (CTZ) and amoxicillin/clavulanate (AMC) in serum and peripheral tissues by comparing bolus versus continuous administration.

Methods: Sixty patients with iDFUs were randomised into four subgroups according to ATB and administration method: CTZ bolus (CTZ_{bolus}), CTZ continuous infusion (CTZ_{continuous}), AMC bolus (AMC_{bolus}), and AMC continuous infusion (AMC_{continuous}). Once steady-state concentrations were reached, microdialysis was used to assess ATB levels in tissue adjacent to the ulcer. Serum and tissue samples were collected over a 6-h period. Bactericidal activity was assessed by peak concentrations (C_{max}), area under the curve (AUC), and the proportion of time free drug concentrations remained above the minimum inhibitory concentration (fT > MIC). Target thresholds were fT > MIC ≥ 60% for CTZ and ≥ 50% for AMC.

Results: All patients achieved serum fT > MIC targets for CTZ and AMC in 100% of AMC_{bolus} and 89% of AMC_{continuous}. In tissue, target attainment was 60% (CTZ_{bolus}), 73% (CTZ_{continuous}), 79% (AMC_{bolus}), and 83% (AMC_{continuous}). Bolus administration led to rapid serum peaks (5 min) and delayed tissue peaks (30–60 min), with subsequent declines. Continuous infusion produced gradual concentration increases over time.

Conclusions: While all patients achieved serum fT > MIC targets for CTZ and AMC (100% for AMC_{bolus} and 89% for AMC_{continuous}), target attainment in tissue was substantially lower. These findings suggest that although serum pharmacodynamic targets are reliably achieved, tissue exposure remains suboptimal.

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1 | Introduction

Diabetes-related foot disease (DFD) is a late complication of diabetes [1, 2]. The most serious DFD manifestations are infections, which can affect not only superficial soft tissue but also deeper structures, including bones [3], potentially predisposing patients to sepsis and lower-limb amputations [4]. Minor amputations due to infection occur in approximately 40% of patients, and major amputations occur in nearly 20% of patients with infected diabetic foot ulcer (iDFU) [5]. Early diagnosis of infection and prompt initiation of appropriate aggressive therapy are crucial for preventing these complications [6]. Management of iDFU is based on five fundamental pillars: antibiotic (ATB) therapy, surgical treatment, offloading, revascularisation when indicated, and local wound care [1].

ATB therapy should be targeted to achieve maximal effective antimicrobial doses applied for a sufficiently long time [1]. In clinical practice, the bactericidal effect of ATBs is usually estimated according to serum ATB concentrations. However, assessment of maximal concentrations, areas under the concentration–time curves (AUCs), and the proportion of time above the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is also necessary.

ATBs are commonly classified based on their antibacterial activity as dose-dependent, where efficacy depends on peak concentrations, or time-dependent, where efficacy depends on the duration of exposure above the MIC. A third category, where efficacy depends on both concentration and time, is sometimes distinguished [7]. For time-dependent ATBs, the aim is to maximise their bactericidal effect, reflecting the duration during which the ATB concentration at the infection site remains above the MIC. This is characteristic of β -lactam ATBs, which include cephalosporins and penicillins. For these agents, efficacy depends on the duration the ATB concentration remains above the MIC (time above MIC, $tT > MIC$) [7].

Time-dependent ATBs commonly used to treat iDFUs are not routinely monitored. It is essential to measure not only the serum concentrations of ATBs but also their concentrations in peripheral tissues at the ulcer site [1, 7].

The present study, entitled *Diabetic Foot Infection Treated with Antibiotics and its Impact on Gut Microbiota* (DFIATIM; EudraCT No. 2019-001997-27), was conducted with the primary objective of assessing the bactericidal activity of time-dependent antibiotics in serum and peripheral tissues of patients with iDFUs, comparing bolus and continuous modes of administration. To determine peripheral tissue concentrations, the study employed microdialysis, a technique that is not commonly used in clinical research, making this investigation particularly unique. The secondary objective of the DFIATIM study evaluating the impact of antibiotics on gut microbiota will not be presented in this manuscript and will be reported separately—in another publication.

2 | Methods

2.1 | Study Participants

In this single-centre, randomised, prospective, comparative trial, we enrolled 60 patients who met the following inclusion criteria:

age 30–75 years, type 2 diabetes mellitus, iDFU requiring ATB therapy, and iDFU caused by pathogens susceptible to the study ATBs. Exclusion criteria included: hepatic insufficiency; chronic kidney disease (CKD) stage 4–5 based on the KDIGO classification [8]; severe malnutrition; allergy to study ATBs; pregnancy or lactation; presence of an active neoplasm; recent percutaneous transluminal angioplasty; inflammatory bowel disease; malabsorption disease; indication for emergent foot amputation; indication for acute revascularisation due to rapid progression of peripheral arterial disease (PAD) or acute arterial ischaemia; and septic shock. All enrolled patients had iDFUs classified as grade 2–3B/D according to the University of Texas classification system.

Infection was determined based on the following parameters: clinical signs such as phlegmon, oedema, redness, pathological ulcer secretion, deepening of the DFU, and foetor; laboratory markers of infection such as elevated C-reactive protein and leukocytosis; positive bacterial cultures from tissue samples or swabs taken from the base of the iDFU after debridement [1]; and, in several cases, a positive probe-to-bone test [9] and/or positive bone biopsy results.

PAD was diagnosed using a combination of methods: ankle–brachial index (ABI), toe–brachial index (TBI), plethysmography, transcutaneous oxygen pressure (TcPO₂) and duplex ultrasound of the lower-limb arteries.

All enrolled patients were indicated for parenteral ATB therapy with CTZ or AMC, since infection was caused by microbial agents susceptible to these drugs. Patients were randomised into four subgroups according to the type of ATB administration: CTZ_{bolus} ($n = 15$), CTZ_{continuous} ($n = 15$), AMC_{bolus} ($n = 16$), and AMC_{continuous} ($n = 14$). A random allocation sequence was generated by a statistician using a computer programme. The sequence, coded as 0 (bolus) and 1 (continuous), was then provided to examiners.

2.2 | DFIATIM Trial—Study Design

After meeting all inclusion criteria, patients were enrolled in the prescreening phase of the study. A second check of the inclusion and exclusion criteria was then performed. Patients were hospitalised in the internal ward of the Diabetes Centre, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine (IKEM), Prague, where ATB therapy with CTZ or AMC was initiated based on culture results and susceptibility testing. Initially, each patient received standardly at least five bolus doses of the assigned ATB according to the respective summary of product characteristics to achieve steady-state concentrations in serum and peripheral tissue. CTZ was given at 2 g every 8 h and AMC at 1.2 g every 8 h. Once steady-state concentrations were achieved, patients were randomised into two subgroups: bolus administration, with 2 g of CTZ every 8 h or 1.2 g of AMC every 8 h, or continuous administration, with 6 g of CTZ over 24 h or 3.6 g of AMC over 24 h.

On the third day of hospitalisation, the first visit (V1), microdialysis was performed to collect interstitial fluid as described below. Patients then continued their assigned ATB regimen until discharge (V2). Outpatient follow-up visits were scheduled at 1 week (V3), 1 month (V4), and 2 months (V5) post-discharge to

assess ulcer healing and perform other relevant examinations, if necessary. The complete study protocol, including all visits and procedures, is illustrated in the flowchart shown in Figure 1. At each study visit, participants were asked about the occurrence of any harm. However, no significant harms were reported during the study. The study was approved by the ethics committees of IKEM and Thomayer University Hospital (Prague, Czech Republic). All participants provided their written informed consent.

There were no changes to the design, results, or analyses after the study began. Everything was conducted according to the protocol.

2.3 | Microdialysis for Tissue-Level Pharmacokinetics

Microdialysis is a minimally invasive method that enables real-time in vivo monitoring of metabolic, biochemical, physiologic, and pharmacologic processes within living tissues and organs [10]. It has become well-established tool in pharmaceutical research, particularly for studying the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of drugs in peripheral tissues [10]. By allowing continuous sampling of small, water-soluble molecules from the extracellular space, microdialysis provides valuable insights into tissue-level drug concentrations, and has proved especially useful for assessing local ATB levels in peripheral tissues [10, 11].

Conventional serum measurements may not reliably reflect drug availability in tissues. Microdialysis overcomes this limitation by enabling continuous in vivo monitoring of tissue concentrations, providing a clearer picture of local drug exposure. ATBs such as AMC and CTZ, commonly used to treat iDFUs [12], are suitable for assessment using this technique. Microdialysis selectively samples the unbound (free) fraction of the drug in interstitial fluid [11]. For the ATBs tested in the present study, the free fraction is substantial—previous study described CTZ at 90% and AMC at 80%. This fraction largely determines antimicrobial effectiveness at the infection site [7, 13, 14].

Under sterile conditions, a linear microdialysis probe (63 Microdialysis Catheter; M Dialysis AB, Stockholm, Sweden) with a polyarylethersulphone membrane and a 20 kD cutoff [11, 15, 16] was inserted into subcutaneous tissue near the iDFU (Figure 1). The probe was then connected to a linear infusion pump filled with the acceptor solution (Ringer's solution). The perfusate with Ringer's solution then flows through the inside of the membrane, during which it is enriched with ATBs that diffuse from the surrounding tissue into the perfusate along their concentration gradient.

At time 0, ATB administration was initiated via intravenous bolus or continuous infusion. Over the subsequent 6 h, blood serum and interstitial fluid samples were collected simultaneously at regular intervals (Figure 1). All microdialysate samples were immediately frozen and stored at -80°C until analysis. ATB

FIGURE 1 | Flowchart of the study protocol illustrating the patient journey from randomisation to follow-up, detailing the key procedures at each of the five visits (V1–V5). ATB, antibiotic; i.v., intravenous.

concentrations in serum and interstitial fluid were then quantified using capillary electrophoresis.

2.4 | Determination of Antibiotics by Capillary Electrophoresis

The determination of ATBs in serum and microdialysate samples is performed by capillary electrophoresis (CE) in combination with contactless conductivity detection (C4D) [1]. CE is a microscale separation technique characterised by high separation efficiency, low sample consumption, and low laboratory processing requirements, and for these reasons it is often employed for the analysis of body fluids including microdialysate [17, 18]. C4D, as a universal detection technique, is typically used for the sensitive determination of low molecular weight substances that dissociate into ions, such as minerals, amino acids, carbohydrates, amines, organic acids, and many drugs, including ATBs [19].

All serum and microdialysis samples were collected at the clinical site, frozen, and transported to the analytic laboratory. For CE/C4D analysis, 15–20 μL of thawed serum or microdialysate sample was used, which was deproteinised by adding acetonitrile in a ratio of 1:3 v/v. After centrifugation, the supernatant was immediately analysed using CE-C4D methods with limits of quantification of 148 ng/mL for AMX and 339 ng/mL for CTZ in the microdialysate. Further details regarding the determination of ATB in serum and microdialysate using the CE-C4D method are summarised in our previous paper [11, 15, 16].

2.5 | Microbiology Assessment and Bactericidal Activity

Samples for microbiological assessment were obtained from iDFUs after local debridement and immediately transported to the microbiology laboratory. Biological material was inoculated onto a set of culture media, predominantly blood and Schaedler agars. Plates were incubated at 37°C in a thermostat; blood agar was cultured under increased carbon dioxide tension, and Schaedler agar for anaerobes was cultured in an anaerobic environment. Plates were examined on the second and fourth days of incubation.

From day 2 onward, all culture plates were evaluated. Colonies were identified by matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) using the Microflex system (Bruker). This method is rapid, accurate, and widely used in clinical microbiology laboratories. Identified pathogens were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility, primarily using the disc diffusion method. Where necessary, testing was extended to include determination of the MIC. Breakpoints were interpreted according to the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) guidelines. MICs were determined using the VITEK 2 Compact system (bioMérieux) or commercial kits (Erba Lachema). In certain cases, susceptibility testing was performed using the E-test (BioVendor). Reserve antibiotics were tested for highly resistant pathogens. These included ceftazidime/avibactam, cefiderocol, daptomycin, and fosfomycin.

The efficacy of ATB therapy in patients with iDFUs depends on achieving sufficient bactericidal activity. The bactericidal effect was evaluated using the maximum serum concentration (C_{max}), the maximum tissue concentration ($C_{\text{max,tissue}}$), and the area under the concentration–time curve in serum ($\text{AUC}_{24,\text{serum}}$) and tissue ($\text{AUC}_{24,\text{tissue}}$). The AUC, representing the area under the plasma concentration–time curve, varies in shape depending on whether administration is intravenous or oral [7]. The 24-h AUC was estimated using the trapezoidal method over an extended 8-h sampling period. To extrapolate to 24 h AUC, the pre-dose concentration at steady state (C_0 , trough level) was assumed to remain constant until the next dose. Under this assumption, the total AUC_{0-24} was calculated by proportional scaling (rule of three). For the 8-h AUC (AUC_8), concentrations of up to 480 min were used. In the bolus group, the 480-min concentration was estimated from C_0 , assuming that the plasma concentration declined to this level before the next dose. In the continuous infusion group, the 480-min concentration was assumed to be constant and approximated by the value measured at 360 min.

The clinical effect of administered ATBs was evaluated based on the proportion of patients who, during the 6-h period, achieved $\geq 60\%$ or $\geq 50\%$ of the dosing interval with free drug concentrations above the MIC of the causative agent in tissue ($\text{fT} > \text{MIC}_{\text{tissue}}$) or serum ($\text{fT} > \text{MIC}_{\text{serum}}$). These thresholds correspond to CTZ ($\geq 60\%$) and AMC ($\geq 50\%$), respectively. Time above the MIC is the most clinically relevant pharmacodynamic parameter for assessing β -lactam efficacy. Recommended therapeutic targets for achieving a sufficient bactericidal effect are $\geq 50\%$ $\text{fT} > \text{MIC}$ for penicillins and $\geq 60\%$ $\text{fT} > \text{MIC}$ for cephalosporins [1, 7].

2.6 | Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics are presented as medians with first and third quartiles or as counts and percentages. Differences in medians of C_{max} and AUC_{24} were assessed using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. Continuous baseline characteristics and ATB concentrations at each time point were compared using the *t*-test, while differences in categorical variables were evaluated using Fisher's exact test. Given the exploratory nature of the study, all *p*-values are reported without adjusting for multiple comparisons, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant. Analyses were performed using R version 4.1.1 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). Anonymised study data are available upon request.

Artificial intelligence was used **exclusively for language editing** and was not involved in the generation of textual content or visual materials.

3 | Results

The baseline characteristics of the study cohort are presented in Table 1. More men were included, consistent with the higher prevalence of DFU in men [1]. There were no significant differences between the groups or their subgroups in baseline characteristics, except for weight and body mass index (BMI; $p = 0.023$). The $\text{AMC}_{\text{bolus}}$ group had the lowest mean BMI (29.7 ± 4.6), whereas the $\text{CTZ}_{\text{continuous}}$ group had the highest mean BMI (35.3 ± 5.1).

TABLE 1 | Baseline characteristics of the study population.

	CTZ _{bolus} (n = 15)	CTZ _{continuous} (n = 15)	AMC _{bolus} (n = 16)	AMC _{continuous} (n = 14)
Age (years)	67 ± 10	65 ± 10	60 ± 7	68 ± 9
Male (%)	80	87	81	86
BMI (kg/m ²)	32.4 ± 3.8	35.3 ± 5.1	29.7 ± 4.6	33.7 ± 5.7
Renal function (glomerular filtration in mL/s)	1.19 ± 0.28	1.24 ± 0.39	1.22 ± 0.44	1.25 ± 0.39
Weight (kg)	106 ± 16	119 ± 21	97 ± 17	109 ± 16
TcPO ₂ (mmHg)	44 ± 17	47 ± 15	48 ± 11	46 ± 15
ABI DPA	1.23 ± 0.25	1.12 ± 0.51	1.20 ± 0.34	1.05 ± 0.27
ABI PTA	1.24 ± 0.19	1.15 ± 0.40	1.15 ± 0.24	1.08 ± 0.3
CRP (mg/L)	42 ± 67	13 ± 14	16 ± 22	23 ± 32
Creatinine (µmol/L)	92 ± 19	95 ± 34	103 ± 50	92 ± 36

Abbreviations: ABI, ankle-brachial index; BMI, body mass index; CRP, C-reactive protein; DPA, dorsalis pedis artery; PTA, posterior tibial artery; TcPO₂, transcutaneous oxygen pressure.

TABLE 2 | The most frequently isolated pathogens from ulcerations in patients with infected diabetic foot ulcers.

Pathogens	Number of isolates	% of patients
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	19	32%
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	15	25%
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	9	15%
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7	12%
<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>	6	10%
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	4	7%
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	4	7%

Microbiological evaluation and specification were performed in all study subjects. A total of 48 different microbial isolates were identified. Polymicrobial infections were observed in 60% of cases. The most frequently isolated pathogens were *Enterococcus faecalis* (n = 19), *Staphylococcus aureus* (n = 15), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (n = 9), *Escherichia coli* (n = 7), and *Streptococcus agalactiae* (n = 6). Resistant strains were detected in 13 cases (21.7%). A detailed overview of isolated pathogens is provided in Table 2.

The time course of mean ATB concentrations in serum and tissue is shown in Figure 2, respectively. Bolus administration led to rapid rises in concentration, with serum peaks observed at 5 min post-administration for both CTZ and AMC, and tissue peaks at 30 min for AMC and 60 min for CTZ. These values then gradually declined but remained significantly higher than those achieved with continuous administration for up to 2 hours with AMC and 3 hours with CTZ. In contrast, continuous administration resulted in a gradual increase in concentrations over the measured period, reaching levels comparable to bolus administration after 3 hours in serum and 4 hours in tissue.

Both maximal concentrations (C_{max}) and AUC₂₄ were higher in the bolus groups compared with the continuous groups

across all scenarios, mostly reaching statistical significance. Importantly, all patients achieved ≥ 60% fT > MIC with CTZ, and almost all patients (except one in the continuous administration group) achieved ≥ 50% fT > MIC with AMC in serum. In tissue, the corresponding rates were 60% versus 73% with CTZ and 79% versus 83% with AMC for the bolus and continuous groups, respectively (Table 3).

4 | Discussion

In routine clinical practice, serum concentrations are usually monitored only for dose-dependent antibiotics. Time-dependent ATBs, including penicillins and cephalosporins, which are commonly used to treat infections in iDFUs [1], are not routinely monitored. Data on the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of these agents in the serum and peripheral tissues of patients with iDFUs are limited. Verifying the tissue availability of these ATBs in this patient population is essential for assessing their therapeutic effectiveness. Additionally, it is important to determine whether different administration regimens (bolus vs. continuous infusion) of selected time-dependent ATBs affect the pharmacodynamic endpoints that predict clinical efficacy.

To date, only a few studies have examined ATB concentrations in tissues. Most have relied on single-point measurements from resected tissue or bone samples [20]. The introduction of microdialysis techniques has enabled a more detailed assessment of the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of ATBs, particularly in the peripheral tissues of patients with DFUs. In 2010, Traummüller et al. reported the use of microdialysis to measure extracellular linezolid concentrations in the soft tissues of patients treated with ATB for severe diabetic foot infection. Based on established pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic (PK/PD) targets, linezolid administered at 600 mg twice daily proved effective in this setting [21]. The same research team later applied microdialysis to assess tissue concentrations of daptomycin. Although PK/PD targets for daptomycin in tissues have yet to be firmly established, the authors concluded that intravenous administration of daptomycin at 6 mg/kg of body weight once daily can be considered effective [22].

FIGURE 2 | Serum and tissue concentrations of tested antibiotics over time. (A) Serum concentrations of tested antibiotics over time following bolus or continuous administration. (B) Tissue concentrations of tested antibiotics over time following bolus or continuous administration. AMC, amoxicillin/clavulanate; CTZ, ceftazidime; NS, not significant. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

However, both studies focused on ATBs that are not routinely used in daily podiatric practice. In our setting, penicillins and cephalosporins are used more frequently, primarily due to the predominance of Gram-positive pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative pathogens, including *Pseudomonas* spp., commonly isolated from iDFUs [1, 12, 21]. In addition to ATB selection, availability, and bactericidal activity, application of dynamic testing and microdialysis techniques to evaluate their pharmacokinetics is of particular interest.

Previous studies have assessed only bolus administration of ATBs in this context [21, 22].

Only one study has investigated the effectiveness of continuous ATB administration. In 2004, a Czech research group measured serum concentrations of AMC in patients with DFUs, correlating these levels to modelled parameters of *Staphylococcus aureus* growth and killing. Continuous intravenous infusion was associated with a more rapid reduction in bacterial load

TABLE 3 | Pharmacokinetic parameters comparing bolus versus continuous administration of ceftazidime (CTZ) and amoxicillin/clavulanate (AMC).

CTZ				
Characteristic	Overall (N = 30)	Bolus (n = 15)	Continuous (n = 15)	p value
Cmax, serum	121 (46, 191)	187 (136, 222)	46 (32, 56)	< 0.001
Unknown	4	0	4	
Cmax, tissue	11 (7, 16)	16 (13, 23)	7 (4, 10)	< 0.001
Unknown	0	0	0	
AUC24, serum (trapezoid)	954 (665, 1350)	1119 (830, 1372)	855 (617, 1002)	0.10
Unknown	4	0	4	
AUC24, tissue (trapezoid)	160 (120, 206)	199 (155, 258)	120 (66, 177)	< 0.001
Unknown	0	0	0	
≥ 60% fT > MIC, serum	26 (100%)	15 (100%)	11 (100%)	> 0.9
Unknown	4	0	4	
≥ 60% fT > MIC, tissue	20 (67%)	9 (60%)	11 (73%)	0.7
Unknown	0	0	0	
AMC				
Characteristic	Overall (N = 30)	Bolus (n = 16)	Continuous (n = 14)	p-value
Cmax, serum	55 (11, 114)	85 (60, 151)	7 (6, 11)	< 0.001
Unknown	4	0	4	
Cmax, tissue	3.9 (1.8, 8.3)	7.8 (4.9, 13.4)	1.6 (1.1, 2.8)	< 0.001
Unknown	1	0	1	
AUC24, serum (trapezoid)	205 (147, 305)	269 (197, 591)	140 (116, 149)	0.001
Unknown	4	0	4	
AUC24, tissue (trapezoid)	44 (23, 96)	76 (37, 132)	23 (17, 40)	< 0.001
Unknown	1	0	1	
≥ 50% fT > MIC, serum	22 (96%)	14 (100%)	8 (89%)	0.4
Unknown	6	2	4	
≥ 50% fT > MIC, tissue	21 (81%)	11 (79%)	10 (83%)	> 0.9
Unknown	3	2	1	

Note: Data are presented as medians and interquartile ranges, unless otherwise noted. *p* values were calculated using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. Counts and percentages are presented for categorical data, with *p* values calculated using Fisher's exact test.

compared with intermittent dosing, while frequent oral administration was found to be potentially effective against susceptible strains [23].

In the present study, both bolus and continuous administration of CTZ achieved effective ATB concentrations (time above MIC) in serum in patients with iDFUs. In peripheral tissue, effective concentrations were slightly more frequent in the continuous group (73% vs 60%), although the difference was not statistically significant. For AMC, clinically effective concentrations were achieved in 100% of cases in serum and 79% in tissue in the bolus group, compared with 89% in serum and 83% in tissue in the continuous group. No statistically significant differences were observed between the administration regimens. While bolus dosing consistently produced the highest peak serum and tissue concentrations (Cmax and Cmax_{tissue}), continuous administration maintained more stable levels over time.

Our results do not fully align with earlier PK/PD data, suggesting that continuous infusion may optimise time-dependent ATBs, particularly β -lactams, by maintaining drug

concentrations above the MIC for a longer duration [24–26]. In our study, both bolus and continuous administration achieved sufficient serum clinical concentrations. However, the higher tissue exposure observed in the bolus groups, as indicated by AUC24_{tissue}, contrasts with the theoretical advantage of continuous infusion, indicating that bolus dosing may still be preferable in certain tissue-penetration contexts.

Interestingly, despite lower peak concentrations and AUC values in the continuous groups, a comparable—or even higher—proportion of patients achieved effective fT > MIC in tissue. This finding may reflect either differences in pharmacodynamics at the site of infection or variability in tissue penetration patterns in iDFU. The use of microdialysis in this study provides a method for assessing local drug exposure and may reveal important nuances in tissue pharmacokinetics not captured by serum measurements alone [27].

The current results of our study do not demonstrate a clear benefit of continuous antibiotic administration compared with bolus dosing. In the evaluated parameters, no statistically or

clinically significant differences were observed between the antibiotic dosing strategies (bolus vs. continuous infusion) regarding their impact on the treatment outcomes of infection in patients with DFU. From a practical perspective, the bolus antibiotic administration may be considered favourable because a continuous type of antibiotic application is difficult to implement in routine inpatient care. Continuous antibiotic administration is associated with increased nursing workload, higher personnel demands, and continuous attachment of the patient to an infusion system, effectively confining the patient to the bed for the entire duration of therapy. Because of the absence of superior clinical outcomes with continuous administration, we strongly support maintaining the commonly used bolus regimen, which is more practical and feasible while providing comparable therapeutic efficacy.

Also, a key factor is the severity of peripheral arterial disease (PAD), since advanced ischaemia likely leads to reduced antibiotic availability in the tissue [16]. However, simply increasing the antibiotic dose may not be an effective strategy in such cases and could be associated with a higher risk of systemic toxicity. Therefore, the vascular status of the limb, including the degree of PAD, should always be carefully assessed before initiating antibiotic therapy. If significant ischaemia is present, optimisation of perfusion through revascularization procedures may be a more appropriate strategy than dose escalation. Increased blood flow can enhance antibiotic availability at the site of infection and increase the likelihood of achieving therapeutic concentrations and then optimal podiatric outcomes.

The tissue concentrations of CTZ and AMC are influenced by pharmacokinetic and patient-specific factors (hydration status, body composition, renal and hepatic function etc.) [26]. These hydrophilic ATBs are primarily distributed in extracellular fluid. They also have relatively low protein binding –10% for CTZ and 20% for AMC—resulting in a larger free fraction available for tissue penetration [26]. In ischaemic tissues, ATB penetration may be significantly impaired [28, 29]. Local inflammation and pH changes in iDFU can increase vascular permeability but at the same time may also impede ATB diffusion [29].

As already mentioned, individual patient-specific factors, such as renal and hepatic function, influence serum and tissue concentrations of ATB [30]. In patients with elevated BMI, distribution volume increases mainly due to expanded extracellular fluid rather than adipose tissue, which may lower plasma and tissue concentrations if dosing is not adequately adjusted [31].

A strength of this study is the use of microdialysis in a real-world clinical setting, allowing for direct comparison of serum and interstitial concentrations in patients. The randomised design and inclusion of two commonly prescribed ATBs further improved the generalisability of the findings.

4.1 | Limitations

However, the study has several limitations. The relatively small number of participants per subgroup (14–16) reduces statistical power and the ability to detect differences. Given that there are many examinations for each patient, many samples are obtained

and further processed, and given the overall complexity of microdialysis, such sample sizes for these types of trials are typical. Given that this is a single-centre study, the results may be biased by local patient characteristics and clinical practice.

The next limitation of this study is that only infections caused by pathogens susceptible to the investigated antibiotics were included. Although this approach was methodologically appropriate for pharmacodynamic target assessment, it restricts the generalisability of our findings. Nevertheless, the two investigated antibiotics represent among the most frequently used antibiotics in the treatment of diabetic foot infections. In clinical practice, infected diabetic foot ulcers are frequently polymicrobial and often involve resistant pathogens, which may substantially affect antibiotic exposure–response relationships and tissue target attainment. Therefore, our results primarily apply to targeted therapy in infections with confirmed susceptibility and may not fully reflect real-world empirical treatment scenarios.

Although microdialysis is a suitable method for assessing pharmacokinetics in tissues, it is not without limitations. Factors such as probe location, local perfusion, and differences in tissue composition can affect the measurement of interstitial ATB concentrations. To minimise these factors, all procedures were standardised (identical equipment, the same application team, and a uniform sampling protocol) for all participants.

Another problem is the relatively short 6-h monitoring period after ATB administration, which may not be entirely the complete drug exposure profile, especially in the case of continuous infusion. Extending the sampling time could reveal further differences between administration modes. Performing 24-h monitoring of ATB concentrations using microdialysis inserted near the iDFU is almost impossible. During the microdialysis procedure, patients must remain bedridden, with the limb immobilised in a fixed position. This can lead to psychological discomfort, back pain, limited self-care, and an increased risk of pressure ulcers. Even during the 6-h protocol used in this study, compliance with these requirements proved to be a significant challenge for some patients. Lastly, parameters such as vascular status (presence of PAD), iDFU healing over time, infection severity, and comorbidities were assessed, but fall outside the scope of this report. These will be presented in a separate article.

Author Contributions

Radka Jarošíková wrote the manuscript, researched data, and coordinated the study, including microdialysis catheter placement, collection of study samples, and patient visits. Dominika Sojáková, Michal Dubský, Andrea Němcová, and Veronika Wosková reviewed and edited the manuscript. Simona Antalová and Pavol Beca provided the antibiotics and performed the pharmacological calculations. Petr Tůma managed the microdialysis technique. Jan Polák processed the microdialysate samples. Istvan Modos and Jan Mareš performed the statistical analysis of the study data. Jakub Mrázek and Chahrazed Mekadim performed testing of stool samples for microbiome analysis. Markéta Skružná processed the culture samples microbiologically and determined MIC values. Vladimíra Fejfarová coordinated the study, including microdialysis catheter placement, collection of study samples, and patient visits, and contributed to the preparation of the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data are available on request from the authors.

Peer Review

For transparency, the peer review documents associated with this article are available at <https://doi.org/10.1002/dmrr.70185>.

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